

Behaviour of Bituminous Concrete Mixes Utilizing Fly Ash

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Abstract: Fly ash from the Thermal Power plant is generated in huge amounts in India. The physical characteristics of fly ash fulfill the standards given out in Ministry of Road Transport and Highways specifications for mineral fillers. This study investigates the potential use of fly ash, as well as cement and traditional quarry stone dust from Granite stone, as mineral fillers in bituminous pavement construction. The Marshall methodology was used to prepare bituminous concrete grading-2 mixes with four different percents of the three kinds of fly ash mineral fillers (FAMF). Marshall stability tests is used to investigate the volumetric and mechanistic properties of bituminous concrete grading-2 (BC-2) mixtures. According to the findings, fly ash has high potential for usage as mineral fillers in bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures.

IndexTerms – Bituminous concrete; Mineral Filler; Fly ash

I. INTRODUCTION

A significant number of research projects in highway engineering deal with material replacement using industrial wastes. In bituminous concrete mixtures, fillers are fine mineral particles mixed in with the coarse and sand aggregates. Many industrial by-products, most of which pass through a 0.075 mm sieve (1), are used as mineral fillers in bituminous mixes, which enhances the performance of the mixture. Because fillers affect the physical and mechanical properties of mixes as well as their composition, they are essential in the production of asphalt (2–4). Large amounts of foundry sand, stone dust, copper slag, and other industrial by-products can be utilized for production of asphalt concrete, especially in developing countries like India. Industrial by-product materials can serve as a technique for disposing of byproducts while also reducing construction and maintenance costs. The United Nations (UN) Basel Convention on the Transboundary Movement of Industrial by-products and Waste Management (5) states that copper slag (CS) is not a harmful material. Water-cooled copper slag has a lower density than air-cooled copper slag due to its porous surface structure, which allows it to absorb more moisture (6).

Using fly ash as a mineral filler (FAMF), the behaviour of bituminous concrete mixtures substituting conventional material with 0,25,50,75, and 100% of industrial by-products is assessed in this study using Marshall test equipment.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Materials

The aggregate gradation in our research work is summarized in Table 1.

In this investigation, the VG-30-viscosity grade from the MRPL oil refinery was used [14]. The properties of VG-30 bitumen are presented in Table 2.

2.2 Objectives and methodology

The purpose of this study is to evaluate fly ash's potential as a mineral filler (FAMF) in bituminous concrete mid limit grade 2 mixtures through laboratory testing. The mechanistic properties (stability and flow) and Marshall volumetric (Voids analysis) of BC-2 mixes containing 0,25,50,75, and 100% FAMF were also investigated.

Table 1. Aggregate gradation for Bituminous concrete grading – 2 mixtures

IS Sieve size (mm)	Range of gradation	Percentage Retained on sieve sizes (Mid limit)	Percent of FAMF content
19	100	10.5	
13.2	79-100	10.5	
9.5	70-88	17	
4.75	53-71	12	
2.36	42-58	9	
1.18	34-48	9	

0.6	26-38	9	
0.3	18-28	7	
0.15	12-20	9	
0.075	4-10	7	0, 25, 50, 75 & 100

Table 2. Properties of VG-30

Description	Results
Penetration value @ 25°C, 0.1mm	68.33
Softening point in °C	51.75
Ductility value @ 27 °C in cm	82.5
Specific gravity(Sp.gr) @ 27 °C	1.00
Flash Point in °C	260.0
Viscosity test @ 135°C in cst	390.0

Table 3. Physical properties of materials

Test	Test Results
Sp.Gr. of FAMF	1.98
Specific surface area of FAMF, cm ² /gm	2987
Specific surface area of Cement, cm ² /gm	3181
Specific surface area of stone MF, cm ² /gm	2838

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 5 presents the results of the Marshal Experiments on bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures made with different percentages of industrial by-products using fly ash mineral filler (FAMF). Using 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100% fly ash mineral fillers, the test results for bituminous concrete grading-2 mixtures were used to determine the optimum binder content. The following sections provide a description of how fly ash mineral fillers affect the various bituminous concrete grading-2 mixing parameters.

Table 4 Mixture Parameters relative to 4 percent air voids for FAMF

Marshall Parameters	Type of MF	FAMF content, Percentage				
		0	25	50	75	100
Optimal bitumen content, %	FAMF	5.48	5.50	5.51	5.54	5.58
Air voids, %	FAMF	4.17	4.02	4.09	4.04	4.07
Marshall Stability, KN	FAMF	23.16	23.02	22.58	22.43	22.27
Flow, mm	FAMF	3.63	3.70	3.60	3.74	3.71
Bulk Density, g/cc	FAMF	2.370	2.358	2.354	2.351	2.348
Voids in Mineral Aggregates, %	FAMF	17.18	17.07	16.79	16.64	15.60
Voids Filled with Bitumen, %	FAMF	75.75	75.32	76.29	76.80	80.63

Theoretical Specific Density, g/cc	FAMF	2.48	2.48	2.47	2.46	2.42
Marshall Quotient, KN/mm	FAMF	6.37	6.41	6.52	6.71	6.89

3.1 Effect of FAMF on optimal bitumen content

Table 5 displays the mixtures' optimal bitumen content (OBC) when designed with 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100% FAMF. The OBC measured with 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100% of IBP-MF exhibits a similar pattern as both the OBC and the FAMF concentration in the BC-2 combination increases. Furthermore, it is found that, in comparison to BC-2 mixtures with 0% IBP-MF, the OBC, which refers to 4% air void, is somewhat greater for BC-2 mixtures with 25, 50%, 75%, and 100% FAMF. This could be because, in comparison to conventional material, the FAMF particle in the combination had a greater specific surface area, which increased the OBC.

3.2 Effect of FAMF on Marshall Stability value

Table 5 shows that when the FAMF content in the BC-2 mixture increases, the stability values for the BC-2 mixtures incorporating FAMF decreases. Additionally, compared to BC-2 mixtures with typical mixtures (0 percent IBPMF), the stability value for mixtures with 25, 50, 75, and 100% FAMF is found slightly lower.

3.3 Effect of FAMF on Flow value

Table 5 illustrates the flow value variation with 0, 25, 50%, 75%, and 100% of FAMF. It is found that in the BC-2 mixture, the Flow value of the mixture increases as the FAMF increases. This is a result of the mixture's high specific surface area particle replacing regular material with lower specific areas.

3.4 Effect of FAMF on Bulk Density

Table 5 illustrates how FAMF affects the bulk density of the compacted BC-2 mixtures. When compared to conventional mineral filler materials, BC-2 mixtures containing FAMF have lower bulk density values. This is because the BC-2 mixture made using conventional materials (cement and stone dust) has a higher specific gravity than the fly ash mineral filler, and the mixture's theoretical specific gravity is lower as well.

IV. CONCLUSION

The examination of bituminous mixes' mixture design characteristics using FAMF and conventional materials yielded the following observations.

- Because of its high specific surface area, fly ash mineral filler has raised the optimum bitumen content of bituminous concrete mixtures.
- When compared to bituminous concrete mixtures made of conventional materials, the bituminous concrete mixture incorporating FAMF has considerably raised the OBC, increasing the cost of production.
- The Ministry of Road Transport and Highways 4th Revision specification's Marshall Stability criteria was satisfied by adding FAMF to the grade-2 mixture of bituminous concrete.

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